

Release notes - Validation Assistant rules EU_PPP

IUCLID 6 version 10 – April 2026

EU Plant Protection Products (PPP)

NEW 10 QLT rules checking study results values have been introduced in the following OHTs of the Chemical Active Substance dataset:

- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.FlashPoint
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.Explosiveness
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.OxidisingProperties (gases, liquids, solids)
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.LongTermToxToFish
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BioaccumulationAquaticSediment
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SedimentToxicity
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToBees
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.ToxicityToSoilArthropods

IMP BR_PPP_062, QLT_PPP_094, QLT_PPP_128, QLT_PPP_123, QLT_PPP_006. Validation messages have been improved.

IMP QLT_PPP_013. The rule was updated to remove the following endpoints from the check:

- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.FieldStudies
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.OtherDistributionData
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BiodegradationInWaterAndSedimentSimulationTests
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.PhototransformationInAir
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.TransportViaAir
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.LongTermToxToFish
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.LongTermToxicityToAquaInv
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.SedimentToxicity
- ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.BioaccumulationAquaticSediment

IMP QLT_PPP_170. The rule was reactivated and the check was extended to all units available for microorganism active substances.

IMP QLT_PPP_127. The rule has been activated for chemical active substance applications.

IMP QLT_PPP_128. The rule was updated due to format changes and activated for the main product dataset in chemical active substance applications.

IMP BR_PPP_058. The rule has been deactivated for MRL applications.

IMP BR_PPP_001, BR_PPP_002, QLT_PPP_040. The rules were updated to add the following endpoint to the check:

ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AnalyticalProfileOfBatches

IMP QLT_PPP_032. The rule was updated to remove the following documents from the check, as they are no longer applicable due to format changes

FLEXIBLE_RECORD.AnalyticalInformation
FLEXIBLE_RECORD.BioPropertiesMicro

Commented [GB1]: QLT_PPP_003 needs to be updated to check the endpoint as well, but the rule is more sensitive as it is used in DWD regulation

Proposal from ECHA: release the rule with a known issue that is missing the endpoint from the check

Commented [GB2]: The document FLEXIBLE_RECORD.BioPropertiesMicro was also removed from the check, since the document shifted to being a summary and we created an ESR

IMP Updates to the scenario matrix of Validation Assistant

○ MRL applications

The scenario matrix has been updated to account for new fields in the dossier header:

'MRL application on minor crops': when selected, a limited set of rules is activated

'Joint Submission' fields: If Member or Contributor is selected as 'Role of the joint submission', a limited set of rules is activated

'Purpose of the application': if one of the following values is selected, a limited set of rules is activated

- include an active substance in Annex IV
- amend existing residue definition
- evaluation of confirmatory data following review according to Article 12 of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005

○ Chemical and Microorganism active substance applications

The scenario matrix has been updated to account for a new field in the dossier header

'Confirmatory information': when selected, a limited set of rules is activated

FIX

The issue affecting the following rule have now been fixed.

QLT_PPP_007. The rule is now checking the correct values of the specified field

Known issue and future improvement

QLT_PPP_003 will be updated to account for `ENDPOINT_STUDY_RECORD.AnalyticalProfileOfBatches` in the future IUCLID releases.

Commented [GB3]: QLT_PPP_003 needs to be updated to check the endpoint as well, but the rule is more sensitive as it is used in DWD regulation

Proposal from ECHA: release the rule with a known issue that is missing the endpoint from the check